

Transfusion Transmitted Diseases in a Blood Bank at Tertiary Care Hospital: A Retrospective StudyArchana T. Tribhuvan¹, Meera S. Mahajan², Chandrashekhar P. Bhale³¹Junior Resident, Department of Pathology, M.G.M Medical College & Hospital, Chh Sambhajanagar, Maharashtra, India²Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, M.G.M Medical College & Hospital, Chh Sambhajanagar, Maharashtra, India³Professor & Head, Department of Pathology, M.G.M Medical College & Hospital, Chh Sambhajanagar, Maharashtra, India

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Introduction:** Blood Transfusion-transmitted Diseases (TTDs) refer to Diseases that can be transmitted through blood transfusions. Transfusion is an irreplaceable therapeutic modality, widely applied to medical care which is a life-saving procedure. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the Seroreactivity of HIV, HBV, and HCV among blood donors.**Materials and Methods:** A retrospective study was carried out over a period of 4 years from January 2019 to Dec 2022. Serum samples were screened for Hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg), antibodies to Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) 1 and 2, Hepatitis C virus (HCV).**Results:** A total of 12498 blood donors were included out of which majority of donors were male (96.31%). The overall Seroreactivity was 1.49%, whereas the Seroreactivity of HIV, HBV and HCV were 0.45%, 0.67% and 0.37%, respectively.**Conclusion:** For reducing transfusion transmitted diseases, the strict selection criteria of blood donors and comprehensive screening of donor's blood using standard methods should be highly recommended for ensuring the safety of blood for recipient and judicious use of blood products should be emphasized.**Keywords:** Seroreactivity, Hepatitis B virus, Hepatitis C virus, Human Immunodeficiency Virus.

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Introduction

Blood Transfusion-transmitted diseases (TTDs) refer to diseases that can be transmitted through blood transfusions. Transfusion is an irreplaceable therapeutic modality, widely applied to medical care which is a life-saving procedure. Transfusion therapy has been the mainstay of several medico-surgical therapeutics since 1930 [1]. There are three types of blood donors [2] : 1) Voluntary / Unpaid 2) Family / Replacement, and 3) Paid.

A voluntary blood donor intentionally donates blood without pursuing any remuneration, whereas a replacement donor is requested to do so by the patient or his associates [3]. Through blood transfusions millions of lives are saved each year. However, blood transfusions are associated with certain risks that can lead to adverse consequences. It may cause acute or delayed complications and carries the risk of the transmission of diseases that might be fatal rather than that of saving life [4]. With the discovery of transfusion-transmissible diseases (TTDs) a new era in blood transfusion medicine

worldwide is started with emphasis on two main objectives: safety, and protection of human life [5]. These diseases include viruses, bacteria, parasites, and other pathogens that may be present in the donated blood and can subsequently infect the recipient. Transfusion-transmissible diseases (TTDs) namely, Hepatitis B virus (HBV), Hepatitis C virus (HCV), Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), and syphilis are major challenges to blood transfusion services. These viruses create a big challenge for blood safety because of their prolonged viraemia, carrier, latent state and chronic state, and life-threatening complications.

According to World Health Organization (WHO) Global Database on Blood Safety (GDBS) 2008, total around 91.8 million blood donations are collected annually. But, approximately 48% of these emanate from high-income countries, stringent to 15% of earth's population. Ten nations vouch for 65% of blood collections worldwide, and India is the third highest bidder in this respect following

United States and China [6]. With almost 9.8 million units of yearly collections and 84% voluntary donors, India is expected to bang on the WHO target of 100% voluntary donations by 2020, much before due date [7]. In the United States (USA) alone, 13.6 million units of whole blood and red blood cells are collected and nearly 21 million blood components are transfused yearly [8]. In Europe, 18,374,971 units of red blood cells were donated, and 20,674,603 transfusion so occurred in 2017 [9].

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the Seroreactivity (presence of antibodies or antigens indicating infection) of HIV, HBV, and HCV among blood donors.

This assessment helps to understand the epidemiological trends of these diseases within the donor population, which can inform strategies for improving screening protocols and blood safety measures.

Material and Methods:

The present study was carried out to find out Seroreactivity of Transfusion Transmitted Diseases (TTD's) in voluntary blood donors at a tertiary care hospital.

Research Setting: Tertiary Health Care Centre.

Study area: Blood Bank, Department of Pathology, MGM Medical College & Hospital, Chhatrapati Sambhajanagar, Maharashtra, India.

Study Design: Retrospective, observational study.

Study Period: The present study was done during 1 January 2019 to 31st Dec 2022.

Study population: Voluntary donors attending Blood Centre and camps organized by MGM Medical College & Hospital, Chhatrapati Sambhajanagar, Maharashtra,

Sample Size: Retrospective study. Data was collected from January 2019 to December 2022. Total blood donors enrolled in the study were 12,498.

Ethical consideration: Ethical permission was obtained from institutional ethics committee and Scientific Advisory Committee of MGM Medical College and Hospital Chhatrapati Sambhajanagar, Maharashtra, India.

Inclusion Criteria: Blood samples from voluntary donors attending Blood Centre and camp as per donor questionnaire

Exclusion Criteria: As per blood donor rejection criteria.

Data Collection: The retrospective data was collected from Master register of Blood Centre, MGM Medical College & Hospital, Chatrapati Sambhajanagar.

Methodology:

The present study was retrospective from January 2019 to December 2022. Retrospective data was collected from Master register of Blood Centre for statistical analysis.

The study included voluntary blood donors who attended Blood Centre and camps organized by the institute in MGM Medical College & Hospital, Chatrapati Sambhajanagar. Donor selection and deferral criteria were strictly followed for the selection of blood donors. Blood samples collected in sample tubes from the donors were tested for the presence of HBV, HCV and HIV infection by Fully Automated Immunoassay System VITROS ECiQ. The tests were performed as per the manufacturer's instructions provided in the kit. Samples below the cutoff value were considered non-reactive. Equal and above the cutoff values were considered reactive.

Results and observations:

The present study was carried out at a tertiary care blood centre during the period from January 2019 to December 2022. The study includes screening tests for HIV, HBV and HCV. Test was done on 12,498 donors during the 4-year period.

Table 1: Distribution of blood donors according to year and Gender wise

Year	Male No	Female No	Total No
2019	4081	110	4191
2020	2333	56	2389
2021	2118	104	2222
2022	3505	191	3696
Total	12037	461	12498

In present study majority of blood donors i.e. 4191(33.5%) were from year 2019, followed by year 2022 i.e. 3696 (29.61%) and 2389(19.1%) blood donors in year 2020 whereas minimum blood donors were reported in year 2021 i.e. 2222(17.8%). Majority of male blood donors i.e. 4081(33.9%) were from year 2019 whereas majority of female blood donors i.e. 191(41.4%) were from year 2022.

Table 2: Distribution of Blood donors according to Gender

Gender	No. of blood donors	Percentage
Male	12037	96.31
Female	461	3.69
Total	12498	100%

Out of 12498 blood donors, male blood donors i.e. 12037(96.31%) were predominant as compared to female blood donors i.e. 461(3.69%).

Table 3: Percentage of Seroreactivity of transfusion transmitted diseases in blood donors

Total number of blood donors	Seroreactivity of transfusion transmitted diseases	Percentage
12, 498	187	1.49%

The percentage of Seroreactivity of transfusion transmitted diseases (HIV, HbsAg & HCV) was 1.49%.

Table 4: Year wise distribution of Seroreactivity of blood donors

Year	HIV	HCV	HBV	Total
2019	23(0.55%)	17(0.41%)	35(0.83%)	75 (0.67%)
2020	07(0.29%)	18(0.75%)	12(0.50%)	37(0.45%)
2021	10(0.45%)	07(0.31%)	13(0.58%)	30 (0.37%)
2022	16(0.43%)	05(0.13%)	24(0.64%)	45(0.37%)
Total	56(0.45%)	47(0.37%)	84(0.67%)	187(1.49%)

Maximum 0.55% of HIV Seroreactivity in blood donors was observed in year 2019 and minimum 0.29% of HIV Seroreactivity was observed in year 2020. Whereas Maximum 0.75% of HCV Seroreactivity in blood donors was observed in year 2020 and minimum 0.13% of HIV Seroreactivity was observed in year 2022. Whereas Maximum 0.83% of HBV Seroreactivity in blood donors was observed in year 2019 and minimum 0.50% of HIV Seroreactivity was observed in year 2020. HIV Seroreactivity accounted for 0.45% in total donors. HBV Seroreactivity accounted for 0.67% in total donors. HCV Seroreactivity accounted for 0.37% in total donors.

Discussion:

Out of 12498 blood donors, male blood donors i.e.12037 (96.31%) was predominant as compared

to female blood donors i.e. 461(3.69%). Similar findings were observed by Chandekar SA et al [10] that most of the donors were males 70,363 (91.79%). These findings were comparable with other studies of Buseri et al [11], Anjali et al [12], which observed more than 90% of male donors in their studies. Whereas Changqing Li et al [13] found contrast findings higher rate of female donors of about 44.5% which was accredited to increased knowledge regarding the blood donation. In present study female blood donors were minimum due to medical unsuitability, anemia, pregnancy, breast feeding, underweight, malnourishment, low deposit of iron, low blood pressure and other health problems. Also, minimum female blood donors may be due to culture and belief, including the fact that because women regularly lose blood during menstruation [14].

Table 5: Comparison of Seroreactivity of transfusion transmitted diseases among blood donors in different studies

Authors	Seroreactivity
Kaur et al [15] (2010)	3.8%
Amrutha et al [16] (2011)	2.81%
Mukherjee et al [17] (2020)	2.70%
Prakash P et al [18] [2016]	1.52%
Present study	1.49%

In present study the percentage of Seroreactivity of transfusion transmitted diseases was 1.49%. Similar Seroreactivity was observed by Prakash et al [18] which noted an overall prevalence of 1.52%. Whereas more overall Seroreactivity was reported by Kaur et al [15] (3.8%), Amrutha et al [16] (2.81%) and Mukherjee et al [17] (2.70%).

Table 6: Comparison of Seroreactivity of HIV, HCV and HBV among blood donors in different studies

Authors	HIV	HCV	HBV
Rajat Mondal et al [19] (2015)	0.14%	0.66%	0.45%
Khaneta Parveen et al [20] (2017)	1.30%	1.04%	3.05%
Rehana Ahmed et al [21] (2020)	0.09%	2.07%	1.6%
Present study	0.45%	0.37%	0.67%

In present study, 0.67% blood donors were HBV reactive where less i.e. 0.45% Seroreactivity of HBV was observed by Rajat Mondal et al [19] and more Seroreactivity of HBV were observed 3.05% and 1.60% by Khaneta Parveen et al [20] and Rehana Ahmed et al [21] respectively.

In present study, 0.45% blood donors were HIV reactive where less i.e. 0.09% Seroreactivity of HIV was observed by Rehana Ahmed et al [21] and 0.14% by Rajat Mondal et al [19] more Seroreactivity of HIV were observed 1.30% by Khaneta Parveen et al. HCV Seroreactivity was observed more i.e. 0.66%, 1.04% and 2.07% respectively by Rajat Mondal et al [19], Khaneta Parveen et al [20] and Rehana Ahmed et al [21] as compared to present study i.e. 0.37%.

Conclusion:

In the present study, the overall Seroreactivity of transfusion transmitted diseases was 1.49% over a study period of four years. In total donors, majority of Seroreactivity was accounted for HBV i.e. 0.67% followed by HIV in 0.45% of blood donors and HCV 0.37% in total donors. Maximum Seroreactivity was seen in the year 2019. Seroreactivity was predominant in male as compared to female.

For reducing transfusion transmitted diseases, the strict selection criteria of blood donors and comprehensive screening of donor's blood using standard methods should be highly recommended for ensuring the safety of blood for recipient and judicious use of blood products should be emphasized.

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